

Context-dependent effects of rosmarinic acid on SH-SY5Y neurite morphology using a label-free, Parkinson's disease-oriented image analysis workflow

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Abstract

Parkinson's disease (PD) pathophysiology includes axonal and neuritic abnormalities, manifested *in vitro* as changes in neurite phenotype. Consequently, the discovery of novel PD drug candidates could be accelerated by accessible, explainable, semi-automated *in vitro* screening assays that prioritize compounds affecting neurite morphology.

The aim of the present study was to develop an image analysis pipeline and use it to study the effects of rosmarinic acid (RosAc), a known neuroactive compound, on neurites and compare them with those of the reference compound, retinoic acid (RetAc). To this end, phase-contrast images of SH-SY5Y cells treated with RosAc or RetAc under varying conditions were obtained and analyzed using a newly developed software pipeline based on pixel classification, followed by operator-curated object filtering based on cutoff-profile optimization and downstream region-of-interest (ROI) and skeleton measurements, implemented in the "PhaseContrastNeuriteAnalyzer" tool. The dependence of neurite changes on proliferation rate, low vs. high fetal bovine serum (FBS) concentrations, and phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) post-treatment was tested.

RetAc treatment at concentrations of up to 10 μM did not inhibit SH-SY5Y cell proliferation, whereas RosAc significantly reduced it, with an IC_{50} of 26.27 μM . RetAc caused significant dose-dependent increases in neurite length only at 1% FBS and not at 10% FBS. This finding both confirmed that low-serum conditions are appropriate for stimulating neuritogenesis and demonstrated that the developed pipeline is capable of quantifying such changes. RosAc induced neurite elongation at 1 μM , but only after PMA post-treatment. Stratification based on the median confluence value indicated that the observed changes were not solely confluence-related artifacts.

In conclusion, the clearest RosAc-associated increase in neurite length occurred at a low concentration after PMA post-treatment, although the effect should be interpreted cautiously because it was modest and partly limited by concentration-dependent reductions in viability and proliferation signals. The developed image analysis pipeline provides an auditable, operator-curated approach for detecting neurite-associated morphology in noisy phase-contrast images and is organized to support reproducibility and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) reuse.

Keywords

Cell proliferation, cell viability, Fiji, ilastik, image segmentation, label-free imaging, neurite morphology, phase-contrast microscopy, retinoic acid, rosmarinic acid, SH-SY5Y

Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) remains a major pharmacological challenge because currently available therapies are symptomatic and have either very limited or no disease-modifying effects (Zafar et al. 2026). There is a pressing need to identify novel therapeutic classes (Yordanov et al. 2026), and improvements in the accessibility, effective content utilization, and scalability of *in vitro* screening approaches could provide a boost in this direction. Better *in vitro* phenotypic "hit" prioritization would allow more effective resource utilization for complex, lower-throughput, and costly disease-relevant models and assays (Bray et al. 2016). In the field of neuropharmacology, axonal and neuritic abnormalities are increasingly recognized as important features of neurodegenerative processes and may precede overt neuronal loss (Burke and O'Malley 2013).

Despite their limited ability to model the full etiology of PD, *in vitro* phenotypic assays are still valuable in PD research because they allow the accessible and scalable generation of first-tier screening data on neuronal phenotypes and stress responsiveness (Simmnacher et al. 2020). Therefore, changes in neurite development, skeleton length, and neurite-like structural integrity can be considered useful surrogate screening endpoints. At the same time, neurite morphology alone cannot provide direct evidence of terminal neuronal maturation, dopaminergic identity, synaptic competence, or disease modification. The best candidates need to be subjected to further *in vitro* mechanistic or *in vivo* assays (Artimagnella et al. 2026). The SH-SY5Y cell line is a widely used model in PD-related pharmacological screening because it is human-derived, easy to maintain, and responsive to differentiation protocols that induce neuronal-like morphology (Ioghen et al. 2023).

Rosmarinic acid (RosAc) is a natural phenolic compound known to exert neuroactive effects, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, and neurogenesis-inducing effects (Ghasemzadeh Rahbardar and Hosseinzadeh 2020; Chen et al. 2024). In PD-relevant contexts, RosAc has been investigated in *in vitro* and *in vivo* models involving oxidative stress (Su et al. 2026), toxicant exposure, mitochondrial dysfunction (Han et al. 2022), or α -synuclein-related (Yamamoto et al. 2023) mechanisms. It has been associated with neurotogenic or neural differentiation-related effects in non-SH-SY5Y systems, such as PC12 cells (El Omri et al. 2010), human amnion epithelial cells (Ferdousi et al. 2019), and Wharton's jelly-derived mesenchymal stem cells (Salmanvandi et al. 2023). RosAc exerts PPAR γ agonistic effects (Fallarini et al. 2009), which are known to affect the neuronal differentiation state (Miglio et al. 2009). These findings do not establish that RosAc can induce retinoic acid (RetAc)-like neurite-associated morphology in SH-SY5Y cells, nor do they define the concentration range or culture context in which such an effect on SH-SY5Y cells might be detectable. However, they make RosAc a plausible candidate for such PD-oriented phenotypic screening.

There are significant methodological challenges in *in vitro* screening for neurite-modifying effects (Serafini et al. 2024). Label-free phase-contrast microscopy is particularly attractive for *in vitro* pharmacological screening because it allows live-cell imaging without fixation, staining, or fluorescent labeling (Kasprowicz et al. 2017). Therefore, it is suitable for real-time and time-series monitoring of neuronal morphology. However, phase-contrast neurite analysis is problematic because thin neurites can be confused with halo effects, shade-off artifacts, uneven backgrounds, local textures, discontinuous fragments, and high-confluence segmentation noise (Kandel et al. 2018). As a result, the direct use of segmentation masks on inherently noisy phase-contrast images can obscure biologically meaningful neurite signals. Recent trainable and deep-learning approaches (Fanti et al. 2011; Pang et al. 2015; Cook et al. 2017; Dias et al. 2017; Kandel et al. 2021; Mencattini et al. 2021; Dang et al. 2024; Musso et al. 2024) have improved model performance, but dataset-specific tuning and artifact sensitivity remain major bottlenecks. Overall, published FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)-compliant instruments and analyses in this field are difficult to find.

The aim of the current study was to determine whether RosAc produces neurite-associated morphological effects in SH-SY5Y cells, whether these effects depend on subsequent phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) exposure, and how they compare with RetAc as a reference differentiating condition. To achieve this aim, the methodological objective was to develop an improved image analysis workflow with operator-curated post-segmentation filtering and to test whether it could quantify neurite-associated morphology in noisy phase-contrast images of SH-SY5Y cells.

Materials and methods

Materials

Rosmarinic acid (RosAc) was provided by Dimitrina Zhelleva, Department of Pharmacognosy and Pharmaceutical Botany, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University–Sofia. All-*trans*-retinoic acid, RPMI 1640, high-glucose DMEM, fetal bovine serum (FBS), phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and resazurin were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. SH-SY5Y cells were obtained from the European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures (ECACC).

Cell culture and treatment

SH-SY5Y cells were used as a human neuroblastoma-derived model capable of neuronal differentiation *in vitro*. Cells were cultured in high-glucose DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and maintained under standard cell culture conditions at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. For the experiments, cells were seeded in 12-well plates at 3×10^4 cells per well. When required by the experimental design, cells were transferred to DMEM

supplemented with 1% FBS. RetAc was used as the reference differentiating agent and was studied mainly at 1 and 10 μM . RosAc was evaluated as the test compound across a broader concentration range (1–200 μM) to capture both lower-dose morphology-associated effects and higher-dose effects on the viability/proliferation readout. Cells were seeded on day 0. RosAc or RetAc was added on day 2. PMA post-treatment, when used, was added on day 4 at a concentration of 16 nM. PMA-only controls received PMA on day 4 without prior RosAc or RetAc exposure. All image-based analyses reported here used images acquired on day 6.

Cell viability and proliferation assay

Cell viability/proliferation was estimated using a resazurin-based metabolic assay after 24 h of treatment (O'Brien et al. 2000). This assay relies on the conversion of resazurin to resorufin by metabolically active cells and was interpreted here as a practical measure of the viable/proliferating cell burden rather than as direct evidence of a specific cell-death mechanism. After treatment, a resazurin solution prepared in PBS was added to each well to a final concentration of 0.001 mg/mL. Plates were incubated for approximately 2 h at 37 °C until visible color development, after which fluorescence was measured using an excitation filter of 485/20 nm and an emission filter of 620/40 nm.

Phase-contrast image acquisition and metadata curation

Live-cell phase-contrast images were acquired from SH-SY5Y cultures under the defined treatment conditions. Each image was linked to structured metadata, including treatment identity, concentration, serum percentage, seeding density, days after seeding, phorbol status, and well identity. Images were captured using an 8-MP CCD camera (Optikam Pro 8LT) mounted on an inverted Optika XDS-2 microscope with X-LED8 illumination. Phase-contrast images were acquired using a 10 \times objective, corresponding to 100 \times total magnification, and had dimensions of 2592 \times 1936 pixels. To minimize intrawell variation in cell density across images, fields were centered equidistantly between the well center and edges. Focus was adjusted to maximize contrast at cell borders and neurite-like processes using a consistent operator-defined criterion.

Computational image analysis pipeline

Image analysis was performed using the custom PhaseContrastNeuriteAnalyzer (v1.0.0, available at <https://github.com/YordanovLab/PhaseContrastNeuriteAnalyzer>), a workflow integrating Fiji/ImageJ (2.16.0/1.54p) (Schindelin et al. 2012), ilastik (1.4.2rc1-gpu-Linux) (Berg et al. 2019), Bash (GNU bash 5.2.21) (Free Software Foundation 2023), R (4.3.3) (R Core Team 2024), plotly (4.12.0) (Sievert 2020), magick (2.9.1) (Ooms 2026) and Shiny (1.13.0) (Chang et al. 2026). An overview of the workflow applied in the current software pipeline is presented in Fig. 1.

Image preprocessing and segmentation

The first step in the pipeline was Fiji/ImageJ preprocessing. It generated red–green averaged images and background-normalized outputs for downstream segmentation. An ilastik pixel classification model, pretrained on images with partial annotations, was then applied to the preprocessed images to produce segmentation masks with background, cell-body, and neurite-like classes. The class-label mapping was checked before downstream quantification to ensure that the pixel-value channels for neurites, cell bodies, and background were interpreted correctly. Mask-area quantification was performed using the segmentation masks. For each image, the percentages of pixels assigned to neurites, cell bodies, and background were calculated. Confluence was derived as the non-background fraction. These variables were used both as image-level covariates and as the basis for validation-image selection.

Validation image selection and manual annotation

To construct an expert-guided validation set, segmentation-derived image-level summaries were first calculated, including neurite-area percentage, cell-body area percentage, background percentage, and confluence. Images were automatically stratified according to neurite percentage and confluence, and representative extreme cases spanning high or low neurite burden and high or low confluence were selected. These four quadrants were used to enrich the validation set with both images likely to contain true neurites and images in which segmentation noise might be misclassified as neurites. Selected validation images were visually reviewed by the operator and labeled as predominantly “signal” when neurites were correctly recognized, predominantly “noise” when artifacts were misclassified as neurites, or “not sure.” The manual labels were not used to retrain the ilastik pixel classifier. Instead, they were used to optimize a post-segmentation ROI acceptance profile.

ROI and skeleton feature extraction

From the candidate neurite masks, Fiji/ImageJ was used to extract object-level ROIs and generate skeletonized representations. ROI objects were imported into R using RImageJROI (Sterratt et al. 2024), and ROI and skeleton summaries were combined with metadata and mask-derived image features. For each ROI, shape and size descriptors were calculated, including area, circularity, aspect ratio, and related morphological features. Skeleton-derived descriptors included skeleton length, branching-related summaries, fragmentation-related summaries, and topology-related measures. Dominant-path and meshness-like summaries were used as interpretable indicators of whether a candidate object resembled a long, neurite-like structure or a more sponge-like, nonspecific segmented network. These ROI- and skeleton-level descriptors formed the feature space used for post-segmentation filtering.

Figure 1. Image analysis workflow for preprocessing, cutoff-profile optimization, model application, and downstream interpretation.

Cutoff-profile optimization and model selection

The central algorithmic step of the workflow was post-segmentation cutoff-profile optimization. Expert-reviewed validation labels and ROI and skeleton descriptors were combined in R, and candidate ROI-retention rules were evaluated by grid search (Wickham et al. 2023, 2024). The optimization did not rely on a black-box classifier. Instead, it systematically searched threshold combinations across interpretable object-level features and scored candidate profiles

according to their ability to retain biologically plausible neurite-like signals while suppressing visually confirmed noise.

Several scoring modes were considered, including “basic” ROI-level filtering, continuity-aware filtering, topology-aware filtering, and ensemble-style profiles. The basic mode relied mainly on ROI-level size and shape descriptors. The continuity-aware mode favored the retention of longer, less fragmented neurite-like structures. The topology-aware mode incorporated additional penalties for sponge-like or mesh-like object geometry that was more consistent with nonspecific segmented noise than with biologically plausible

neurites. Ensemble profiles combined complementary retained-ROI sets from multiple scoring modes. The grid search was implemented transparently in R using base statistical functions together with table-processing packages such as `dplyr` (Wickham et al. 2023) and `tidyr` (Wickham et al. 2024). The full scoring formulas are provided in the Suppl. material 1 and GitHub software repository.

Application of selected profile to full image set

After visual inspection of the candidate profiles and confirmation of acceptable performance, the selected cutoff profile was applied to all segmented images. Images used during `ilastik` training or cutoff-profile optimization were excluded from the final biological interpretation analyses to reduce overfitting. The resulting retained-neurite outputs were merged with image metadata and used for downstream statistical analysis.

Statistical analysis

Concentration-dependent effects on the resazurin signal were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test. The apparent RosAc IC_{50} was estimated separately by nonlinear regression using a four-parameter logistic model fitted to the normalized resazurin signal. Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed on numeric image-level variables after centering and scaling, and missing numeric entries were handled conservative-

ly by median imputation when required for matrix-based analysis. Because retained skeleton length and related morphological variables were frequently right-skewed, both parametric and rank-based group comparisons were considered. Kruskal–Wallis analyses with pairwise Wilcoxon rank-sum post hoc tests were used according to the plotted comparison structure, and pairwise post hoc comparisons were adjusted using the Holm procedure. For adjusted modeling, ANCOVA-style linear models with partial drop-one F testing were used to estimate the relative contributions of treatment identity, concentration, phorbol status, and selected image-level covariates to the retained total skeleton length.

Results

Validation image selection and manual annotation

The first major result concerned the image analysis workflow itself. The initial step of raw `ilastik` segmentation frequently identified neurite-like structures that were visually implausible, especially in high-confluence fields or images with local texture and phase artifacts. For this reason, the segmentation output was treated only as an initial candidate map rather than as the final neurite measurement. The distributions of initial segmentation-derived cell-body area, neurite area, and confluence values across images were examined (Fig. 2). The initial neurite-area

Figure 2. Histograms showing the distribution of images by neurite-area percentage and confluence percentage after `ilastik` pixel classification. The dot plot at the bottom shows representative candidate images (outlined), including visually confirmed neurite-signal “choice” examples (green outlined circles) and visually confirmed “noise” examples (red outlined circles).

Figure 3. Representative neurite-identification examples after ilastik segmentation alone (red outlines) and after post-segmentation cutoff filtering (green outlines). The basic cutoff profile is shown in the upper two rows of images and the ensemble continuity–topology profile in the lower two rows.

percentage showed an approximately symmetric distribution with mild right skew, whereas confluence was approximately symmetrically distributed. The dot plot shows the identified representative extreme image combinations based on confluence and neurite area. The most compact and uniform group identified was the group with low confluence but high neurite area. In contrast, the most variable group was the group with both high neurite area and high confluence.

Validation-group sampling across the neurite-area and confluence quadrants was followed by visual expert review, which generated a curated set of “choice” and “noise” examples. Images labeled internally as “choice” corresponded to signal-predominant examples. Images labeled as “noise” had few correctly identified neurites and predominantly contained misclassified artifacts. In most selected subgroups, the initial neurite-area and confluence values were similar between signal-predominant and noise-predominant examples. A clear separation in confluence values was observed only between the two selected “choice” images and one “noise” image in the high-confluence and high-neurite group. In the low-neurite/low-confluence group, the selected examples showed visibly lower and non-overlapping confluence values compared with examples from the low-confluence/high-neurite group.

Cutoff profile optimization and selection

Representative image overlays showed that ilastik segmentation alone retained many candidate ROIs that only partially resembled neurites upon visual inspection or did not resemble them at all. The post-segmentation cutoff step reduced this problem by applying additional ROI- and skeleton-level acceptance rules. Both the basic and ensemble cutoff-filter models were applied to the same set of selected validation images (Fig. 3). The basic cutoff profile was relatively conservative and effectively eliminated obvious noise, but it also retained too few neurite structures. The ensemble model was continuity- and topology-oriented, retained more neurite-like ROIs, and was more sensitive to slightly curved or branched structures. However, for this reason, it misclassified more artifacts as neurites. Across the current curated set of selected “choice” and “noise” examples, the largest number of retained ROIs after the application of each cutoff-filter model was observed in the high-neurite, low-confluence group. In addition, at low confluence, the most pronounced misclassification of noise as neurites was observed after application of the ensemble model. With this model, the gain in sensitivity required cautious interpretation of difficult images, in which some false-positive objects could still be retained.

Figure 4. Distribution of ROI-level skeleton lengths in validation images classified by ilastik segmentation before and after cutoff filtering. Red points represent candidate ROIs before filtering, and green points represent retained ROIs after cutoff filtering. Medians (rhombi) and means (triangles) of retained skeleton lengths are shown as summary markers to illustrate the skewed ROI-length distribution.

Application of selected profile to full image set

All aggregated neurite ROIs from the validation images were compared across both models before and after cutoff filtering (Fig. 4). At the ROI level, candidate skeleton lengths were strongly right-skewed, with many short objects, which were likely predominantly noise, and relatively few long structures, which were likely elongated neurites. This pattern supported the use of median and distribution-aware summaries for further comparisons rather than reliance only on mean values. Before cutoff filtering, the majority of neurite ROIs had very short lengths, and this was attributable to noise particles to a significant extent. In the high-neurite groups, which mostly comprised low-confluence images, a minority of ROIs with substantially increased lengths were also present and represented visually plausible neurite-like structures. With both cutoff models, the retained ROI distributions showed that cutoff filtering enriched for longer and more neurite-like skeletons while reducing the contribution of short candidate objects. The basic cutoff model showed better discrimination between visually plausible neurites and confluence-associated artifacts. However, because it retained too few visually plausible neurites, the resulting image-level summaries were more vulnerable to the influence of outliers and may have generalized poorly beyond the validation set. The ensemble model was less specific and retained more confluence-associated false-positive structures, but it also recovered severalfold more visually plausible neurites. Thus, it was selected as the more suitable compromise for application to the full dataset.

Exploring influence of measured variables in relation to neurite lengths

After generalization of the ensemble cutoff profile across all images, an initial exploratory PCA was performed to examine whether the retained-neurite feature space

contained group-level biological structure and to compare the influence of all measured morphological and neurite-related parameters across the treatment and control groups (Table 1). The analysis aimed to clarify how each parameter influenced the separation among treatment groups and controls. Obtaining PCA dimensions and loadings was helpful for exploring whether the differences were primarily attributable to changes in neurite-related features, technical confounders, or other biologically relevant features. Because PCA was performed on the same dataset used for downstream comparisons, it was interpreted only as exploratory support for endpoint selection rather than as independent validation.

Table 1. PCA loadings of retained-neurite, topology, and image-composition features.

Feature	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
retained_roi_count	0.19	0.23	0.45	0.23
image_total_skeleton_length	0.22	0.22	0.45	0.15
neurites_percent	-0.03	-0.32	0.38	0.05
retained_roi_fraction	0.2	0.3	0.32	0.15
confluence	-0.1	-0.43	0.25	0
cell_bodies_percent	-0.11	-0.42	0.23	0
mean_circularity	-0.28	0.16	0.2	-0.35
mean_meshness_score	-0.27	0.21	0.19	-0.43
mean_dominant_path_ratio	-0.28	0.12	0.19	-0.28
mean_area	0.27	0.12	0.17	-0.4
mean_skeleton_length	0.38	-0.1	0.03	-0.24
mean_aspect_ratio	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.43
median_skeleton_length	0.36	-0.15	-0.1	-0.18
background_percent	0.1	0.43	-0.25	0

The first identified principal component (PC1) explained approximately 37% of the variation and was positively associated with the mean and median skeleton lengths of retained ROIs per image. PC2 explained approximately 27% of the variation and was primarily related to confluence. PC3 explained approximately 14% of

the variation and was predominantly associated with the number of retained neurites and the sum of their lengths. PC4 explained approximately 8% of the variation and appeared to be associated with neurite shape, branching, and the number of retained ROIs.

Exploratory multivariate analysis supported the biological usefulness of the retained-neurite feature space while also showing its limitations (Fig. 5). Across 154 image-level observations, the PC1–PC3 space showed moderate treatment-associated structure, with a separation eta-squared value of 0.18 and nearest-centroid agreement of 0.58. Treatment centroids were displaced relative to one another, but the overlap among image clouds remained substantial, indicating that the morphological signal was informative at the group level without functioning as a clear per-image classifier. Total retained skeleton length per image was selected as the primary metric because it integrates both the length and abundance of retained neurite-like structures while reducing reliance on single-ROI measurements.

Neurite length across FBS concentrations and RetAc treatment

The effects of two different FBS concentrations on neurite-length changes induced by RetAc treatment were compared (Fig. 6). In the 10% FBS environment, neither 1 nor 10 μM RetAc produced changes in neurite length compared with the controls. However, upon decreasing the FBS concentration in the culture medium to 1%, there was a statistically significant and dose-dependent increase compared with both the controls and the respective treatment groups with 10% FBS. The control median was 1,076 px, compared with 7,758 px for 1 μM RetAc and 14,197

px for 10 μM RetAc. As previously shown, the ensemble cutoff model applied here could be affected by confluence; therefore, whether the differences were retained after stratification of the data according to the median confluence value was examined. This approach showed that the direction and magnitude of the significant effects remained consistent after median-confluence stratification.

Cell viability and proliferation after RosAc and RetAc treatment

To provide biological context for interpreting the observed neurite changes, the effects of both the test and reference compounds on viability and proliferation, as measured using the resazurin assay, were studied (Fig. 7). RetAc was tested only at concentrations of up to 10 μM , a concentration range commonly used to induce SH-SY5Y morphological differentiation. For the test compound RosAc, a broader concentration interval was intentionally studied to provide an overview of its effects on neurites across concentrations. Under the present assay timing and concentration range, RetAc did not significantly reduce the resazurin viability or proliferation signal, although some treatment groups showed increased intergroup variability among samples. Despite the high variability in the control group, RosAc decreased the resazurin signal across the entire concentration interval applied. To determine whether these differences resulted from cytotoxicity rather than reduced proliferation associated with differentiation or cell-cycle arrest, phase-contrast images were visually examined. Complete cell death was observed at 200 μM . At 100 μM , the cultures contained predominantly rounded cells with morphology suggestive of cell

Figure 5. PCA score plot of PC1 vs. PC3 based on image-level retained-neurite features generated by the ensemble cutoff workflow.

Figure 6. Total retained skeleton length per image across RetAc treatment conditions under low-serum (1% FBS) and high-serum (10% FBS) culture conditions, with additional stratification by median confluence (bottom two rows). Statistical tests and significance symbols refer only to the combined all-confluence plots. Asterisks (*) indicate within-FBS-group comparisons with the matched control using Holm-adjusted pairwise Wilcoxon rank-sum tests following Kruskal–Wallis analysis; number signs (#) indicate across-FBS comparisons for the same plotted group and are shown only above the higher group. */# $p < 0.05$; **/## $p < 0.01$; ***/### $p < 0.001$.

Figure 7. Concentration-dependent effects of RetAc and RosAc on SH-SY5Y cell viability/proliferation. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test for comparisons with the matched untreated control. Significance symbols indicate Dunnett-adjusted comparisons. *** $p < 0.001$.

stress or an activated cell-death program. At 50 μM , the cultures contained mostly elongated cells, with a smaller area occupied by rounded cells. At concentrations of 25 μM and below, the predominant appearance indicated that cell death was not prevalent and that the differ-

ences were primarily proliferation-related. This observation justified interpreting the morphological dataset primarily through lower-concentration conditions, under which extensive viability or proliferation loss was less likely to dominate the image-level phenotype.

Figure 8. Total retained skeleton length per image across RetAc and RosAc treatment conditions under low-serum culture conditions (1% FBS), grouped by differentiating agent, concentration, and PMA exposure, with additional stratification by median confluence. Statistical tests and significance symbols refer only to the combined all-confluence plots. Asterisks (*) indicate comparisons within the PMA-presence group with the matched control using Holm-adjusted pairwise Wilcoxon rank-sum tests following Kruskal–Wallis analysis; number signs (#) indicate across-PMA comparisons for the same plotted group and are shown only above the higher group. */# $p < 0.05$; **/## $p < 0.01$; ***/### $p < 0.001$.

Neurite length after RosAc and RetAc treatment

The effects of RosAc on total retained neurite length were analyzed together with the influence of PMA post-treatment. For comparison, RetAc and untreated controls were also included (Fig. 8). In the absence of PMA post-treatment, RetAc caused a dose-dependent increase in total retained skeleton length, with significant differences compared with the untreated control. PMA post-treatment reduced the RetAc-associated increases, eliminating the significant effect at 1 μM and attenuating it at 10 μM . RosAc did not produce consistent significant changes without PMA, except for an apparent increase at 50 μM that was likely driven by an influential outlier in a small sample. After PMA post-treatment, RosAc produced visible increases in retained neurite length at 1 and 10 μM , with the strongest shift at 1 μM . At 1 μM RosAc, the median total

retained skeleton length increased from 1,517 px without PMA to 4,000 px with PMA. However, the comparison with the matched PMA-treated control remained of borderline statistical significance after multiple-comparison adjustment. Therefore, the RosAc effect was interpreted as a modest PMA-dependent morphological shift rather than as robust RetAc-like neuritogenesis.

To assess the factors associated with variation in total retained skeleton length, an ANCOVA-style analysis was also applied (Table 2). The treatment agent was the strongest statistically significant contributor after controlling for all other factors. First-agent concentration and PMA post-treatment had smaller but significant effects. The mean meshness score and mean dominant-path ratio contributed negligibly and were not statistically significant. Neurite-area percentage, cell-body area percentage, and confluence were removed because of linear dependence and collinearity with other image-composition variables.

Table 2. ANCOVA-style adjusted analysis of total retained skeleton length per image under 1% FBS, restricted to first-agent concentrations of 1 and 10 μM . Terms were evaluated using partial drop-one F tests. Partial η^2 indicates the proportion of residual explainable variance attributable to each term after accounting for the other retained predictors. Normalized impact size is the square-root transformation of partial η^2 , scaled from 0 to 1.

Model term	df	F value	p value	Partial η^2	Normalized impact size
First treatment agent	2	39.90	1.56×10^{-14}	0.36	0.60
First-agent concentration	1	5.87	0.02	0.04	0.20
PMA	1	4.68	0.03	0.03	0.18
Mean meshness score	1	0.33	0.57	0.002	0.05
Mean dominant-path ratio	1	0.05	0.83	<0.001	0.02
Neurites percent	0	—	—	—	—
Cell bodies percent	0	—	—	—	—
Confluence	0	—	—	—	—

Discussion

The current study demonstrates that the PhaseContrast-NeuriteAnalyzer workflow can quantify RetAc-associated neurite outgrowth from noisy, label-free phase-contrast images of SH-SY5Y cells. Application of this workflow to RosAc showed a modest, PMA-dependent increase in retained neurite length at 1 μM . In contrast, PMA post-treatment reduced the RetAc-associated increase in total retained skeleton length under the tested conditions.

RetAc is the best-known differentiating compound for neuroblastoma cell lines, including SH-SY5Y. It induces differentiation through the activation of retinoid receptors (RAR/RXR) and downstream PI3K/Akt signaling (López-Carballo et al. 2002). RetAc causes growth arrest, likely by downregulating the MYCN oncogene, which is typically upregulated in neuroblastoma (Zimmerman et al. 2021). RetAc has been shown to induce SH-SY5Y differentiation toward a predominantly cholinergic phenotype, with the formation of prolonged, branched neurite outgrowths accompanied by cell-cycle arrest (Kovalevich and Langford 2013; Artimagnella et al. 2026). An early phase 1 clinical trial (NCT02438215) suggested that the oral RXR agonist IRX4204 improved motor symptoms in patients with early-stage PD over a 30-day period (Sanders et al. 2016). Although this finding does not directly validate RetAc-treated SH-SY5Y cells as a PD model, it illustrates broader interest in retinoid signaling as a PD-relevant pharmacological axis and supports the sensitivity of the current model to the effects of such compounds on neurites.

The effects of FBS supplementation in the culture medium on MYCN expression are cell type-dependent and might be influenced by confounding factors. High-serum conditions have repeatedly been shown to oppose SH-SY5Y neuronal differentiation and favor a less mature phenotype, whereas low serum concentrations promote retained skeleton length. This may reflect serum-derived growth-factor signaling and the maintenance of proliferative transcriptional programs, although the exact contribution of MYCN under the present SH-SY5Y conditions was not directly tested (Rezekina et al. 2025). The results confirmed that increases in SH-SY5Y neurites occurred only at 1% FBS and not at 10% FBS. To provide optimal permissive conditions for sensitive morphometric analysis, 1% FBS was used for all RosAc experiments. MYCN levels are inversely correlated with parkin expression in the developing mouse and human brain (West et al. 2004). Parkin has protective effects in PD by helping cells clear defective proteins. RetAc leads to parkin upregulation in neuroblastoma cells (Aydin et al. 2024). Future work could test whether RetAc- or RosAc-associated morphological changes coincide with altered PRKN/parkin expression in SH-SY5Y cells or more disease-relevant models.

PMA is a constituent of croton oil known to activate diverse protein kinase C (PKC) isoforms. It is known to promote growth arrest, morphology-associated changes, and neuronal-marker shifts. Its addition after RetAc is usually intended to stabilize the differentiated cellular

state and promote cell survival. However, previous studies have shown conflicting results regarding the predominant neuronal subtype induced by this approach (Presgraves et al. 2003; Prisacar et al. 2025). The results showed no significant increases in overall neurite length compared with the controls after treatment with PMA alone. However, PMA introduced variability, which could be explained by the opposing and highly context-dependent effects of activating multiple coexisting PKC isoforms. Activation of isoforms such as ϵ can promote differentiation and neurite growth. Other isoforms, such as δ and θ , can elicit apoptosis, whereas classical isoforms, such as α and β , can promote cell survival, likely because of downstream MAPK/ERK pathway activation (Zeidman et al. 1999). PKC α and PKC β have been shown to be the most abundant isoforms in SH-SY5Y cells, and after PMA differentiation, the α and ϵ isoforms are downregulated (Leli et al. 1993). The weak neuroprotective effects suggested for rasagiline in PD may be partially attributable to PKC α upregulation (Weinreb et al. 2004). RetAc itself has been shown to decrease PKC α activity through phosphatidylserine competition (Radomska-Pandya et al. 2000). The use of PMA to stabilize differentiated *in vitro* cultures may therefore reflect the activation of prosurvival pathways, although its effects remain strongly context-dependent.

The current study shows that RosAc causes more pronounced inhibition of proliferation and viability than RetAc at the concentrations typically used to induce differentiation *in vitro*. The most relevant RosAc concentrations for morphological studies were those at the lower end of the tested range, especially 1 μM . The neurite-analysis results from RosAc-treated SH-SY5Y cells showed a context-dependent effect that was manifested only after PMA post-treatment. Several studies using non-SH-SY5Y *in vitro* models have suggested that RosAc can influence neural induction, neurite-associated behavior, or neurogenesis-related signaling. These observations were obtained by treating PC12 cells, stem cells, or injury- and neurogenesis-inducing models in different signaling environments. RosAc is known to be a PPAR γ agonist, with an EC $_{50}$ of approximately 56 μM (Han et al. 2017). A direct PPAR γ -mediated explanation is speculative, particularly because the most apparent morphology-associated effect occurred at 1 μM , below the reported PPAR γ EC $_{50}$. Indirect pathway modulation, altered stress responsiveness, or interaction with PKC-sensitive signaling may also contribute. The same study (Han et al. 2017) showed that its cardioprotective effects were reversed by the addition of a PPAR γ inhibitor. PPAR γ activation induces neuroblastoma differentiation *in vitro* (Vella et al. 2016) and remains one possible mechanism, but the concentration mismatch means that this explanation requires direct testing. The dependence of the RosAc effect on neurites on PMA post-treatment might be related to the activation of prosurvival PKC subtypes in SH-SY5Y cells. PPAR γ has been shown to attenuate the cytosol-to-membrane translocation of PKC α in monocytes/macrophages, effectively decreasing its activity (von Knethen et al. 2007). If

a similar effect occurs in RosAc-treated SH-SY5Y cells, it could contribute to the observed PMA dependence. PPAR γ activation has been explored in PD pharmacology, including observational findings suggesting an association between pioglitazone exposure and delayed PD onset (Chen et al. 2022). This association may be attributable to downstream PGC1 α activity and improved mitochondrial function (Jamwal et al. 2021). However, retrospective findings concerning pioglitazone were not confirmed in a randomized trial (NINDS Exploratory Trials in Parkinson Disease [NET-PD] FS-ZONE Investigators 2015). Pioglitazone has been shown to promote neurite growth in SH-SY5Y cells, further supporting their applicability as a first-tier screening model (Miglio et al. 2009).

These results were obtained by analyzing only label-free phase-contrast images of cells cultured in 12-well plates. Analyzing neurite abundance from this type of image is particularly challenging, and the direct use of pixel-classification segmentation approaches typically fails by misclassifying predominant noise as neurites. Previous deep-learning or conventional segmentation-based workflows are valuable and have clearly advanced the field, yet robustness remains a central problem even with the most powerful approaches (Fanti et al. 2011; Pang et al. 2015; Cook et al. 2017; Dias et al. 2017; Kandel et al. 2021; Mencattini et al. 2021; Dang et al. 2024; Musso et al. 2024). The developed image analysis pipeline was intended to address this problem. Instead of assuming that all segmented neurite-like ROIs were equally valid, it added an intermediate filtering step between candidate-object detection and acceptance. An advantage of the pipeline is that the researcher provides auditable expert input by selecting representative signal-predominant and noise-predominant examples for validation, particularly examples in which the initial segmentation-derived neurite signal is driven predominantly by noise. The workflow significantly facilitates this process by providing the researcher with an appropriately focused subset of images for manual review, representing combinations of extreme initial prefiltering neurite-percentage and confluence values. This makes it possible to tune reusable ROI-retention cutoff profiles based on continuity, topology, and ROI morphology while penalizing profiles whose apparent signal separation is driven mainly by variation in confluence. This approach improves the biological specificity of the accepted structures while keeping the human contribution explicit and auditable and reducing black-box behavior. In neurite image analysis studies, results have been reported to be strongly biased by variation in confluence because of object overcrowding and overlap (Lee et al. 2017). The current workflow measures confluence as a primary confounder that was shown to affect the applied ensemble model and thus allows assessment of whether major findings are likely to be driven by image-density artifacts through confluence-stratified visualization. The observed differences in neurite measurements may also be attributable to changes in neurite branching, which

could bias neurite-length measurements after RetAc and RosAc pretreatment. The ANCOVA-style model and PCA did not support this possibility.

The study has several limitations. SH-SY5Y cells are a practical *in vitro* screening system and, as such, do not capture all facets of PD etiology. The results should be interpreted cautiously because neurite-associated morphology is a relevant early phenotypic marker for PD-oriented screening but is not a complete marker of neuronal maturation. RosAc should not currently be viewed as a differentiating agent in this model but rather as a candidate low-dose modulator. The choice of total retained neurite length as a major comparator, although expert-based and relevant, may require further consideration because it was informed by PCA of the same dataset to which it was subsequently applied. The workflow was optimized and evaluated within a single image-acquisition setting, and the selected cutoff profile may not transfer directly to other microscopes, magnifications, illumination conditions, culture densities, or cell types without renewed validation.

The findings should ultimately be followed by validation in more disease-relevant systems, such as toxin-based assays, α -synuclein-related paradigms, mitochondrial stress models, patient-derived neurons, or organoid-based platforms. Future studies should therefore combine the present live, label-free morphology workflow with orthogonal markers such as β III-tubulin, MAP2, TH, and synaptic proteins and, where feasible, transcriptomic or functional readouts. Moreover, the software workflow should be further tested on independent phase-contrast datasets to evaluate how well the optimized post-segmentation acceptance strategy generalizes across image-acquisition conditions and to clarify the robustness of endpoint and variable selection.

Conclusion

The study suggests that RosAc produces a modest, PMA-dependent neurite-morphology shift in SH-SY5Y cells at a low concentration. The findings support further evaluation of RosAc as a candidate low-dose modulator of neurite-associated morphology in PD-oriented screening models. The study also presents a reproducible, operator-curated phase-contrast image analysis workflow that was internally evaluated using RetAc-associated increases in retained neurite length as a positive-control phenotype. The developed pipeline may support PD compound prioritization and may be adaptable to broader neuropharmacological, neurotoxicity, and neurite-morphology studies after dataset-specific validation.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: SH-SY5Y (ECACC catalogue no. 94030304).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following: Claude, GPT.

Used for: Software and automation.

During preparation of this work, the authors used Claude, ChatGPT, and GPT-based coding assistance through Codex for support with code generation, code testing, debugging, and improvement of the image-analysis workflow. The authors reviewed, edited, tested, and validated all AI-assisted code and retained full responsibility for the final software, analyses, interpretation of results, and manuscript content. Generative AI tools were not listed as authors and did not replace author responsibility for the scientific work.

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Author contributions

Siyana Hristova conceived the idea to test rosmarinic acid, performed the laboratory work, including cell culturing and treatments, acquired the phase-contrast images and associated metadata, and contributed to the initial draft generation. Yordanov supervised and directed the study, designed the experiments, made the methodological choices, developed and improved the software workflow, performed the statistical analyses, interpreted the results, and prepared the final manuscript draft. Virginia Tzankova provided the laboratory infrastructure, coordinated the work, and contributed scientific consultation throughout the study. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

The dataset and workflow were organized to support reproducibility and FAIR reuse. The software pipeline is available from the PhaseContrastNeuriteAnalyzer GitHub repository (<https://github.com/YordanovLab/PhaseContrastNeuriteAnalyzer>) (Yordanov and Hristova 2026b), and the dataset is available for download from the Zenodo repository (Yordanov and Hristova 2026a).

Supplementary material 1

Supplementary methods

Authors: Yordan Yordanov, Siyana Hristova, Virginia Tzankova

Data type: docx

Explanation note: Cutoff-profile optimization and model selection.

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